

Employee Attrition Prediction using Machine Learning

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Abstract — Attrition is the departure of employees from the company for any motive consisting of resignation, termination, death, or retirement. This study examines the important elements that influence an employee's decision to leave the company and predicts whether or not a specific employee would resign from their crucial position. Employee turnover occurs when employee strength decreases year by year. The reason for leaving the employees depends only on satisfaction, promotion last 5 years and several projects. This article describes how to use the Gradient Boosting Classifier and Decision Tree Classifier predictive model to predict whether or not employees will leave the company. Kaggle provided the dataset. A combination of data and machine learning algorithms was used to build this model. A machine learning algorithm is used to determine the accuracy of this model.

Keywords—employee attrition, gradient boosting classifier, decision tree classifier, predictive model.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is a common topic in the industry, and excessive drop rates cause a large number of problems within the regulatory framework, such as talent and knowledge loss, training and management expenses, etc. Including workplace, job satisfaction, employer behavior, working time, and most importantly salary or incentive. A gradient boosting classifier was used to train dataset models in this study, and the following reasons for doing the study can be expected if decision tree classifier algorithms are utilized. The current research I did focused on some of the following things like Satisfaction_level, Promotion_last_5years, and the number of projects. Employee resignations are a reality in any business. On the other hand, the loss of essential personnel can lead to a reduction in production if the situation is not handled properly. The organization may need to recruit and train young people with a practical and time-consuming tool. Many organizations are curious to know which employees are at risk of leaving. To maintain a competitive advantage over its competitors, a company must make reducing human losses a priority.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Francesca et al. [1] After a comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms, the Gaussian Naive Bayes classifier was shown to be the best classification method for achieving the analysis' goal. In this investigation, the

Naive Bayes algorithm accurately classified 364 out of 441 occurrences.

Madara pratt et al. [2] Attrition has been predicted using partition trees and random forests. Prior to categorization, the data was pre-processed by Pearson's correlation to remove undesired features. However, when compared to other machine learning techniques, their work demonstrates no improvement in accuracy.

Zangeneh et al. [3] offered a three-point foreclosure structure. They reduced the data in the first phase by using the "max-out" option. They trained a retrospective model to forecast in the second phase. The third stage is confidence analysis, which is used to validate the prediction model. Aside from poor accuracy, the system has a lot of problems with pre-processing and processing.

Usha et al. [4] In order to forecast an employee's likelihood of leaving the organization, researchers compared the Naive Bayes section with the J48 decision tree method. On each algorithm, two techniques were tested: tenfold verification and 70 percent division. With ten-fold verification, J48 had 82.4 percent accuracy and 17.6 percent improper division, whereas, with 70 percent division, it had 82.7 percent accuracy and negative division of 17.3 percent.

Alduayj et al. [5] Random forests, k nearest neighbor, and support vector machines with various kernel functions were utilized as learning models for multiple machines. They made use of three separate IBM HR databases. Although their approach performed well with simulated datasets, it performed poorly with the genuine dataset.

III. METHODOLOGY

Using the data provided, the suggested model would appropriately determine the cause for employees leaving the organization. The form should be able to tell the difference between the reason for employees leaving and the opportunity for employees to depart. The data in the database is split into two categories: training and testing. A decision tree and a gradient boosting classifier will be used to predict whether or not an employee will leave.

The steps to follow are:

1. Data Source.
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Model Evaluate
5. Result and Description

A. Data Source: The data collected in this research paper for attrition prediction came from Kaggle. This database contains 10 features and 14,999 samples. All ten factors are related to these issues. The database contains important features such as satisfaction level, recent upgrade years, and the number of project attributes. This data is used to classify and predict the outcome.

B. Data Pre-processing: This is a step towards the machine learning method for everything. This process includes data cleaning, descriptive analysis, and data segmentation. All this is done to make the data more efficient. The data can be processed to make our model more efficient and accurate.

1. **Data cleaning** Use a variety of information cleaning techniques to collect a set of data. Comment attribute columns are removed from the database after storing new columns containing numeric values extracted from the processed information for forecasting.

2. **Descriptive analysis:** Initiate metadata analysis to identify key attributes and trends that contribute to attrition.

3. **Split the data:** choose a dataset for training and testing, then try out different classification methods on it.

C. Machine Learning: Machine learning (ML) algorithms were tested to separate predicted data. For the ML model, the data was divided into 70% training and 30% testing. The result of the satisfaction level in the model is low, so the employee leaves the job. The chance of employees leaving the job is high. The algorithm that works best depends on the type of problem-solving, the computer resources available, and the type of data.

1. **Gradient Boosting Classifier:** The Gradient Boost classifier is an addition to a base model in which the mistake is repaired through repeated iterations (or stages) and a regression tree is added to fix the residual (previous stage error).

2. **Decision Tree Classifier:** The Decision Tree part uses a decision tree to construct a new model. Each branch descending from that node represents one of the property's possible values, and each node is a test of an attribute.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Model construction is a key process in predicting staff reductions. The steps involved in modeling are:

1. Import packages for implementation

```
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
%matplotlib inline
```

2. Importing the dataset

```
from google.colab import files
uploaded = files.upload()
```

Choose Files HR_comma_sep.csv

• HR_comma_sep.csv(text/csv) - 551786 bytes, last modified: 10/12/2020 - 100% done
Saving HR_comma_sep.csv to HR_comma_sep.csv

```
#Store the data into a dataframe
employee_data = pd.read_csv('HR_comma_sep.csv')
#print the first 7 rows of data
employee_data.head()
```

3. Find the correlation of data for finding the important feature

```
corr_matrix = employee_data.corr()
plt.figure(figsize=(10,10))
sns.heatmap(corr_matrix,annot=True,cmap="YlGnBu",linewidths=4.0)
plt.show()
```


4. Splitting the data into 70:30 ratio test and training data.

```
y=employee_data.left
X = employee_data.drop('left',axis=1)
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.3, random_
```

```
from sklearn import metrics
print("Accuracy:",metrics.accuracy_score(y_test, y_dt_pred))
print("Precision:",metrics.precision_score(y_test, y_dt_pred))
print("Recall:",metrics.recall_score(y_test, y_dt_pred))
```

```
Accuracy: 0.9635555555555556
Precision: 0.9468503937007874
Recall: 0.8973880597014925
```

```
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingClassifier
gb = GradientBoostingClassifier()
gb.fit(X_train, y_train)
y_pred = gb.predict(X_test)
```

```
print("Accuracy:",metrics.accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred))
print("Precision:",metrics.precision_score(y_test, y_pred))
print("Recall:",metrics.recall_score(y_test, y_pred))
```

```
Accuracy: 0.9715555555555555
Precision: 0.958252427184466
Recall: 0.9207089552238806
```

5. Finding the main features using a Decision tree classifier.

```
dt1 = DecisionTreeClassifier(random_state=42,max_depth=5,min_samples_leaf=50)
dt1.fit(X_train, y_train)
y_dt_pred = dt1.predict(X_test)
```

```
feature_importances_ = dt1.feature_importances_
feature_list = list(X)
relative_importances = pd.DataFrame(index=feature_list, data=feature_importances, columns=["importance"])
relative_importances.sort_values(by="importance", ascending=False)
```

	importance
satisfaction_level	0.571739
last_evaluation	0.145911
time_spend_company	0.134703
number_project	0.091590
average_monthly_hours	0.055407
Departments	0.000650
Work_accident	0.000000
promotion_last_5years	0.000000
salary	0.000000

V.RESULT

Employees leave due to low wages, low promotions, a high number of projects, and their knowledge of close to 5. The integration matrix and decision tree revealed that the most important factor is the level of satisfaction. Furthermore, we developed a model with high precision and accuracy, demonstrating that the model can effectively forecast whether an employee will leave the firm.

As per the evaluation, the project number, the previous year's promotion, and the level of satisfaction are employed by critics leaving the company or not, they obtained The Gradient Boosted Classifier had a test accuracy of 0.97 percent and a test accuracy of 0 percent and 0.96 in the Decision Tree Classifier.

VI.CONCLUSION

This research identifies the reasons why employees leave the organization and, more importantly, forecasts the chance of specific employees departing. We used the algorithms are Gradient boosting classifier and Decision Tree Classifier. And among these algorithms, I got the best accuracy with the gradient boosting classifier.

In this case, It would be feasible to generate the basic metrics needed to evaluate everything (accuracy, precision, recall, and so on) and determine the most appropriate category for predicting whether an employee would leave the organization.

VII.REFERENCES

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